

Spontaneous Resolution of a Post-Traumatic Proximal A2 Segment Anterior Cerebral Artery Pseudoaneurysm

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Introduction

Traumatic intracranial pseudoaneurysms are rare consequences of blunt or penetrating head injury and are associated with significant morbidity and mortality. Many are not seen on initial imaging and may appear later, often presenting with catastrophic bleeding days to weeks after trauma. The median delay to diagnosis has been reported to be about 15 days, with 73% identified only after the first week. A high index of suspicion, timely repeat imaging, and early treatment are therefore essential.

Case Presentation

A 33-year-old male was brought to the emergency department after a severe head injury from a motor vehicle accident. Computed tomography revealed extensive maxillofacial and skull base fractures, bifrontal comminuted depressed frontal bone fractures, bilateral frontal hemorrhagic contusions, a large midline basifrontal hematoma, and basal subarachnoid hemorrhage. He underwent craniotomy and evacuation of the right frontal hematoma with elevation and fixation of fracture segments. On day 23, he developed rapid neurological decline. Digital subtraction angiography demonstrated a lobulated pseudoaneurysm with a narrow neck arising from the proximal A2 segment of the left anterior cerebral artery. Re-exploration and hematoma evacuation were performed. A repeat DSA after two weeks showed complete disappearance of the pseudoaneurysm, with the small parent branch no longer visualized. At two months, he remained communicative with mild cognitive impairment and occasional irritability. Six-month follow-up DSA confirmed no recurrence.

Conclusion

A post-traumatic pseudoaneurysm should be considered in patients with severe head injury associated with skull base fracture and subarachnoid hemorrhage who develop delayed neurological deterioration. Early cerebral DSA is warranted, particularly when basal SAH and a “clot within a clot” are present, as these may suggest an underlying vascular injury. Spontaneous thrombosis, although observed in our patient, is an exceptional and unpredictable outcome and should not be used to justify conservative management. Timely diagnosis and appropriate intervention remain essential for improving outcomes.

Keywords

Head injury; intracerebral hematoma; traumatic intracranial pseudoaneurysm; skull bone fracture; cerebral digital subtraction angiography